

Building the Palestinian Social Enterprise in the Digital Era

A Customised Competence Framework

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About EPISODE

The overarching goal of EPISODE is to empower continuing vocational education and training providers to enhance the resilience, digital readiness, and growth of social entrepreneurship, micro-businesses, MSMEs, and early-stage start-ups in Palestine, with a focus on producing public prosperity.

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Executive Summary

This report represents the first public output of the EPISODE project, a 2-year initiative co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union. This report will inform the Training of Trainers (ToT) intervention and the co-design of the learning program on Digital Social Entrepreneurship targeting young, future, and early social entrepreneurs which are part of the project intervention.

This report is based on desk and field research, as well as consultation with stakeholders, and presents a comprehensive competence framework for social digital entrepreneurship that fits actual needs in Palestine, and outlines the competence framework for digital social entrepreneurs in Palestine, in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for individuals to effectively engage in social entrepreneurship within the digital domain. The framework aims to provide guidance for aspiring social entrepreneurs and stakeholders involved in education, training, and support programmes.

The report is an essential reading for TVET providers, private and public organisations active in the field of VET, MSMEs, early-stage start-ups and incubators, as well as policymakers in charge of education and innovation, and is also aimed at teachers, trainers and mentors at vocational education and training institutions, as well as, young, future and early social entrepreneurs with an interest in the future skills needs brought by the digital transformation of the social entrepreneurship ecosystem in Palestine.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	03
Rationale	05
Methodology	06
1. Background Research	08
Definition of Entrepreneurship in the International Context	08
Definition of Entrepreneurship in the Palestinian Context	11
Overview of Digital Education in Palestine	13
Technical and Vocational Education in Palestine	14
Social Entrepreneurship in Palestine	15
2. Data Collection and Analysis	16
3. Competence Identification and Framework Development	17
Spotting Opportunities	19
Mobilising Resources	21
Cultural Awareness	22
Ability to Identify Social Problems	24
Digital Competencies	26
Conclusions	27

Rationale

Self determination and economic independence are two pillars within communities that are needed to ensure a healthy social living standard. In Palestine, such basic pillars are frail due to unequivocally tiresome political, social and economical instability. Furthermore, such factors have created a context specific definition for entrepreneurship in Palestine. Entrepreneurship is not limited to traditional business ventures. It also encompasses social entrepreneurship, which focuses on addressing social and environmental challenges while generating sustainable solutions. Social entrepreneurs in Palestine strive to create positive social impact, promote inclusivity, and contribute to the overall well-being of communities.

After intensive desk research looking into the different definitions and types of entrepreneurship, based on global standards, and local needs, we have come to the concept of subsistence entrepreneurship, which specifically pertains to entrepreneurial activities aimed at meeting basic needs and generating income for survival. This type of entrepreneurship is commonly observed in developing economies or marginalised communities where formal employment opportunities are limited such as in Palestine. Subsistence entrepreneurs typically operate as micro-enterprises, which can include small retail shops, street vendors, or local service providers. Their primary goal is to sustain themselves and their families by earning a livelihood through self-employment.

Although instability has led to creativity, Palestinian entrepreneurs' struggle daily. One major theme that emerged from entrepreneurs' experiences is the impact of security threats on their businesses. The political situation in their respective regions has a profound effect, leading to adverse consequences for business operations. Apart from security concerns, limited access to necessary equipment also emerged as a significant constraint for many businesses in the region. These factors collectively contribute to the challenging environment faced by subsistence entrepreneurs, hampering their ability to grow and thrive.

To develop effective entrepreneurship programs, it is crucial to comprehend how national and community stakeholders perceive entrepreneurship. This understanding is essential for fostering collaboration, establishing ownership, and aligning the program's intentions with the beneficiaries' understanding and appreciation. It ensures that all parties are working together towards the same goals and aspirations. Globally, social businesses and start-ups are recognised as potential solutions to worldwide social problems (Misbauddin and Nabi, 2019). However, despite this trend, the development of necessary skills and competencies for social entrepreneurs in Palestine remains inadequate. Although the national plan encourages digital education, there is a lack of content related to developing digital skills. On the other hand, there are many independent vocational training and education centers, there is little coordination between them and the MoE leaving the vocational pathway lacklustre.

Methodology

The objective of this study is to design a comprehensive competence framework for social digital entrepreneurship that fits actual needs in Palestine. The framework outlines the essential skills, knowledge, and attributes required for individuals to effectively engage in social entrepreneurship within the digital domain. In order to define the EPISODE framework, the following steps were implemented:

1. Background research: This involved the collection and analysis of existing information from previously published sources including definitions, challenges and opportunities to help establish a baseline understanding. background research Also included a review of entrepreneur competencies, digital competencies, and soft social skills.

2. Data Collection and Analysis: During this step, data was gathered from multiple sources, including interviews, surveys, and consultations with stakeholders. Engagement with stakeholders and discussions with leading specialists indicate that both primary and expert insights were actively sought to inform the development of the framework

3. Competence Identification and Framework Development: Based on the data collected and analysed in the previous steps, researchers identified specific competencies related to entrepreneurship, digital skills, and soft social skills. These competencies would then form the basis for developing the EPISODE framework. The framework includes a structured model and guidelines for individuals or organisations to assess and develop these competencies.

4. Validation workshop: The validation workshop is a crucial step to ensure the robustness and accuracy of the developed framework. During this workshop, the framework was presented to a group of experts and stakeholders for review and feedback. The feedback received was used to refine and validate the framework, making sure it aligns with real-world needs and expectations.

Figure 1: Methodology Steps for the definition of the EPISODE competence framework

Step One: Background Research

To determine the necessary competencies for social entrepreneurs in Palestine, we investigated previous internationalisation efforts through comprehensive desk and field research. Earlier studies highlighted variances in the needs across countries, prompting our desk research to explore the perceptions of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship specific to the Palestinian context. Outcomes from this preliminary research informed the design of focus group questions, ensuring they would address the critical issues noted across different nations. One key exposure from our research was the differences in how social entrepreneurship is understood and how a social enterprise is defined. Consequently, questions pinpointing these differences were developed. This exploration not only pinpointed crucial concepts, theories, and pre-existing frameworks concerning social digital entrepreneurship competencies but also laid the groundwork for comprehending the distinct attributes and necessities of digital social entrepreneurship. This involved an exhaustive examination of prevailing literature on social and digital entrepreneurship and competence structures, with a spotlight on the EntreComp and DigComp frameworks. The objective was to determine the skills and competencies essential for EPISODE learners, leading to an adapted hybrid model between both EntreComp, and DigComp frameworks and a detailed modelling of EPISODE competencies.

Definition of Entrepreneurship in the International Context

The European Commission (EC) defines entrepreneurship as a dynamic process that encompasses not only economic activities but also social and cultural dimensions. According to the EC, entrepreneurship involves the identification and pursuit of opportunities, the mobilisation of resources, and the creation of value through innovation, creativity, and risk-taking. It recognizes entrepreneurship as a driving force for economic growth, job creation, and social development.

The EC emphasises the importance of fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and promoting entrepreneurial skills and competencies among individuals of all backgrounds. It believes that entrepreneurship contributes to a more competitive and inclusive society, as it enables individuals to realise their full potential, transform ideas into viable businesses, and make positive contributions to their communities. The EC's approach to entrepreneurship encompasses support for startups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and social enterprises, as well as initiatives to enhance entrepreneurial education, access to finance, networking opportunities, and favourable regulatory frameworks.

¹ For more information about the Lisbon strategy and Europe 2020 strategy visit the official website of the European Commission available on www.ec.europa.eu [accessed 20 December 2011].

On the other hand, the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) offers a definition that primarily centres on business-focused entrepreneurship, decisively excluding social entrepreneurship (OECD, 2007b). This isn't a dismissal of the significance of social entrepreneurship. Instead, it reflects the intent to highlight a specific surface of entrepreneurship related directly to business. This is aligned with the interests of the OECD and its associated entities that have collaborated and supported its initiatives in this area.

The definition encompasses three key elements: Entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurial Activity, and Entrepreneurship

- Entrepreneurs are those persons (business owners) who seek to generate value, through the creation or expansion of economic activity, by identifying and exploiting new products, processes, or markets.
- Entrepreneurial activity is the enterprising human action in pursuit of the generation of value, through the creation or expansion of economic activity, by identifying and exploiting new products, processes, or markets.
- Entrepreneurship is the phenomenon associated with entrepreneurial activity.

Given the wide range of outcomes and expressions of entrepreneurship, it is clear that no single indicator can fully capture its complexity, especially considering the various objectives involved. Similarly, the same applies to measuring the number of entrepreneurs.

The OECD outlines several key capacities for developing entrepreneurship as shown in Figure 2. These capacities include:

- Policy and regulatory framework: Developing entrepreneurship requires an enabling environment with supportive policies, regulations, and institutions. This includes measures such as simplified business registration processes, access to finance, and legal frameworks that protect property rights and promote fair competition.
- Access to finance: Adequate access to finance is crucial for entrepreneurs to start and grow their businesses. Developing entrepreneurship requires creating diverse and inclusive financing mechanisms, including microfinance, venture capital, and angel investment, tailored to the needs of different types of entrepreneurs.

¹ For more information about the Lisbon strategy and Europe 2020 strategy visit the official website of the European Commission available on www.ec.europa.eu [accessed 20 December 2011].

- **Entrepreneurial skills and education:** Building the capacities of aspiring and existing entrepreneurs through education and training is essential. This involves fostering entrepreneurship education at all levels of education, promoting vocational training, and providing mentoring and coaching programs to support entrepreneurs.
- **Research and innovation:** Encouraging research and innovation is important for developing entrepreneurship. This includes promoting collaboration between research institutions, universities, and businesses, creating networks for knowledge exchange, and supporting the commercialization of research outcomes.
- **Networking and collaboration:** Building strong networks and fostering collaboration among entrepreneurs, business associations, and other stakeholders is vital. This includes creating platforms for networking, knowledge sharing, and experience exchange, as well as facilitating partnerships between entrepreneurs and established businesses.
- **Internationalisation and global markets:** Facilitating international trade and access to global markets is crucial for the growth and success of entrepreneurs. This involves providing support for export activities, helping entrepreneurs navigate international regulations and standards, and fostering entrepreneurship with a global outlook.
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** Establishing robust monitoring and evaluation systems helps track the progress of entrepreneurship development efforts and identify areas for improvement. This includes collecting and analysing data on entrepreneurship indicators, evaluating the effectiveness of policies and programs, and using evidence-based approaches to inform decision-making.

These capacities, when developed and supported, can contribute to creating a conducive environment for entrepreneurship to thrive, driving economic growth, job creation, and innovation in developing economies.

The OECD framework (Figure 2) therefore identifies three separate but interconnected flows, all of which are important in the formulation, assessment, and appraisal of policy measures: “determinants”, “entrepreneurial performance”, and “impact”, where: determinants reflect the key factors that affect entrepreneurial performance; entrepreneurial performance reflects the target indicators that policymakers believe have an impact on some or many ultimate objectives (impacts). Each of these is described in more detail below.

Figure 2: OECD Framework

Entrepreneurship is a diverse and dynamic concept that can manifest in various forms and contexts. The different types of entrepreneurship arise from the distinct motivations, goals, and characteristics of individuals or groups engaging in entrepreneurial activities. OECD classifies “Entrepreneurship” in the following types:

- **Subsistence entrepreneurship (Necessity-driven Entrepreneurship)** refers to the type of entrepreneurial activity where individuals or households engage in self-employment or small-scale business ventures primarily to meet their basic survival needs. In subsistence entrepreneurship, the focus is on generating income and sustaining livelihoods rather than pursuing growth, expansion, or profit maximisation. This form of entrepreneurship is often found in economically disadvantaged or marginalised communities where limited job opportunities and resources push individuals to create their own income-generating activities. Subsistence entrepreneurs typically operate in sectors such as agriculture, informal trading, crafts, or services, and their businesses tend to be small-scale and locally oriented. The main goal of subsistence entrepreneurship is to ensure personal or family subsistence and improve living conditions rather than achieving significant economic growth or market dominance.
- **Small Business Entrepreneurship:** In this type of “Small Business”, entrepreneurs typically operate locally and cater to a specific niche or target market. Their focus is on providing goods or services that meet local demand, rather than pursuing rapid growth or innovation. Small businesses play a vital role in local economies and often form the backbone of many communities.
- **Scalable Startup Entrepreneurship (Opportunity-driven Entrepreneurship) :** Scalable startup entrepreneurship refers to the creation of high-growth potential ventures with innovative business models or disruptive technologies. These entrepreneurs aim to build scalable businesses that can quickly expand their market reach and generate significant returns on investment.
- **Large Company Entrepreneurship.** These huge companies have a defined life-cycle. Most of these companies grow and sustain by offering new and innovative products.
- **Social Entrepreneurship:** Social entrepreneurship involves the pursuit of social or environmental objectives alongside financial sustainability. Social entrepreneurs create businesses or organisations that address pressing societal challenges, such as poverty, healthcare, education, or environmental sustainability.

Definition of Entrepreneurship in the Palestinian Context

Entrepreneurship in Palestine can be defined as the process of identifying and pursuing business opportunities to create innovative and sustainable enterprises. It involves individuals or groups who take initiative, bear risks, and mobilise resources to establish and grow new ventures or expand existing ones. In the Palestinian context, entrepreneurship encompasses a wide range of activities, including the establishment of small businesses, startups, social enterprises, and innovative projects.

The definition of entrepreneurship in Palestine is influenced by various factors specific to the region. These factors include the **unique political, social, and economic challenges faced by Palestinians, as well as the aspirations for self-determination and economic independence**. Entrepreneurship is seen as a means to foster economic development, job creation, and societal advancement within the Palestinian context.

In Palestine, entrepreneurship is not limited to traditional business ventures. It also encompasses social entrepreneurship, which focuses on addressing social and environmental challenges while generating sustainable solutions. Social entrepreneurs in Palestine strive to create positive social impact, promote inclusivity, and contribute to the overall well-being of communities.

Moreover, entrepreneurship in Palestine is often driven by innovation, creativity, and the utilisation of technology. Entrepreneurs in various sectors, such as technology, agriculture, renewable energy, and creative industries, leverage innovative approaches and digital tools to overcome constraints and seize opportunities in a dynamic and evolving business environment.

The definition of entrepreneurship in Palestine is not confined to individual endeavours but also includes collaborative efforts and the formation of networks and ecosystems that support entrepreneurial activities. It emphasises the importance of partnerships, mentorship, access to finance, business development services, and policy frameworks that create an enabling environment for entrepreneurial growth.

The definition of Palestine aligns closely with the definitions put forth by the EU and OECD, encompassing the key components mentioned earlier. However, given the prevailing circumstances of occupation and the political situation, certain components such as resilience become even more significant and integral to entrepreneurship in Palestine. This brings us to the concept of subsistence entrepreneurship, which specifically pertains to entrepreneurial activities aimed at meeting basic needs and generating income for survival. This type of entrepreneurship is commonly observed in developing economies or marginalised communities where formal employment opportunities are limited such as in Palestine. Subsistence entrepreneurs typically operate as micro-enterprises, which can include small retail shops, street vendors, or local service providers.

Their primary goal is to sustain themselves and their families by earning a livelihood through self-employment.

One major theme that emerged from entrepreneurs' experiences is the impact of security threats on their businesses. The political situation in their respective regions has a profound effect, leading to adverse consequences for business operations. For instance, in Hebron's old city, an Israeli plot aimed at seizing 70 shops resulted in the evacuation order for a carpentry owner, disrupting their business activities. Moreover, Israeli settlers have been responsible for demolishing five Palestinian shops in Hebron's Old City, further exacerbating the difficulties faced by local entrepreneurs. The general context in the old city of Jerusalem presents additional obstacles, as it obstructs local sales and tourism. Apart from security concerns, limited access to necessary equipment also emerged as a significant constraint for many businesses in the region. These factors collectively contribute to the challenging environment facing subsistence entrepreneurs, hampering their ability to grow and thrive.

Recently, the Palestinian Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Empowerment (MoEE) has been increasingly focusing on promoting and nurturing Scalable Startup Entrepreneurship or Innovation-led Entrepreneurship as a key driver of economic growth and development. The definition revolves around the pursuit of novel ideas, products, or services that have the potential to disrupt existing markets or create new ones. These entrepreneurs are driven by a desire to introduce ground-breaking innovations and capture significant market share. Innovation-led entrepreneurship thrives on technological advancements, creative thinking, and a willingness to challenge the status quo. Startups in Palestine are tech-based or tech-enabled small businesses that have a scalable business model and at least a minimal viable product.

For Palestinians, Entrepreneurship is not just a means of economic empowerment; it is a symbol of resilience, self-determination, and the pursuit of a brighter future.

While the occupation presents its fair share of obstacles, embracing entrepreneurship offers Palestinians a pathway to reclaim autonomy, carve out opportunities, and build enduring enterprises that uplift Palestinian communities. This venture becomes the tool to envision and direct destiny, break free from external reliance, and showcase talents and ground-breaking concepts to the world. Through entrepreneurial pursuits, Palestinians strive to rise above the limitations set before them, fostering a flourishing economy rich in growth, job creation, and societal transformation. At its core, this journey leads towards goals of autonomy and self-sufficiency.

In summary, both stakeholder interviews and the desk review underscore the intricate and multifaceted nature of entrepreneurship in Palestine. The variety in terminology and interpretations underscores the different goals, viewpoints, and hopes of the involved stakeholders.

To develop effective entrepreneurship programmes, it is crucial to comprehend how national and community stakeholders perceive entrepreneurship. This understanding is essential for fostering collaboration, establishing ownership, and aligning the programme's intentions with the beneficiaries' understanding and appreciation. It ensures that all parties are working together towards the same goals and aspirations: Entrepreneurship Programming in Palestine.

Overview of Digital Education in Palestine

The lack of a clear vision, strategy, or laws to regulate and develop digital education and to enhance digital skill levels thwarts effective progress in the West Bank and Gaza. The Palestinian National Policy Agenda (NPA) 2017–22 is the policy pronouncement which comes closest to addressing digital skills. Under Priority No. 6, **“Economic Independence,” the NPA supports and promotes the digital economy and the ICT sectors as business enablers. Other sections recognize the need to build the digital economy through the development of technology clusters. However, the NPA has little content specifically related to digital skills development.** More generally, NPA’s Priority focuses on providing “quality education for all” by enabling access to education for all citizens in the West Bank and Gaza, East Jerusalem, and Area C. It emphasises education at all levels of learning, including preschools, primary (years 1–10) and secondary schools (years 11–12), institutions of higher education, and vocational schools, known as the Technical Vocational Education and Training League (TVET).

The NPA guarantees universal education for children. In addition, it calls for improving the curricula of primary and secondary schools, developing e-learning programs, expanding access to education in marginalised areas, and upgrading educational facilities. It also calls for developing TVET infrastructure and aligning TVET and higher education programs to market needs.

Reports by - and discussions with - international donors and NGOs confirm the necessity of a National Skills Development Strategy as a means to make meaningful advancements in upgrading digital skills among the Palestinian population. Unfortunately, there are few reliable sources of information on the skill levels of school and university graduates. The collection of timely, relevant, and actionable data should be prioritised as a precursor to the development of effective programming.

Technical and Vocational Education in Palestine

Vocational schools play a significant and growing role in the development of skills among Palestinian students and the wider workforce. The schools fall into two separate categories: Vocational Education and Vocational Training.

- Vocational education is the official education provided by the Ministry of Education (MoE) and includes theoretical and practical curriculum.
- Vocational training centers is the non-formal education provided by the Ministry of Labor (MoL), NGOs, continuing education and training centers, and it focus on applied and practical skills.

Both of these tracks are independent, with little coordination between MoE and the vocational training institutions, which leaves labour in the West Bank and Gaza without a clear vocational pathway. The features of the vocational system are detailed below.

Secondary vocational schools and colleges: There are 24 secondary vocational schools in the West Bank and Gaza that provide a two-year program for students in the eleventh and twelfth grades. There are 15 technical colleges in Palestine, (the West Bank and Gaza) offering two-year programs for their students. Students who finish their academic school education in grade 12 and pass the general secondary education examination can also enrol in these colleges.

Vocational Training Centers: These centres provide vocational training, often referred to as non-formal education, to individuals aged 15 and above. Various organisations oversee these vocational centers, curating programs that span a diverse array of specialisations and last between 5 to 24 months. The training predominantly emphasises practical learning, with a maximum of 25% devoted to theoretical instruction. While graduates from these centers are awarded certificates, these don't translate to college credits for advanced studies in higher education institutions.

In the 2018 school year, approximately 51,360 Palestinian students (32 percent female) were enrolled in vocational education programs and 19,359 students were enrolled in vocational training programs. The proportion of female students is increasing each year but their numbers still remain far below those of male students. The number of students enrolled in vocational education and training is growing each year, but this is still lower than the market needs. Culture plays a role in the lower enrollment as vocational education has a negative perception in the West Bank and Gaza. Children preparing to graduate from high school are generally encouraged to pursue university degrees. With the growth of employment opportunities for skilled vocational workers, stakeholders interviewed for this study see a shift. Vocational education is increasingly viewed as a solution to build in-demand skills for employers in Palestine

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The Technical Vocational Education and Training League: TVET is a nongovernmental organisation set up in 2003 headquartered in Ramallah. Its membership includes nongovernmental nonprofit teaching and education organisations. TVET is represented in the Higher Council for Innovation and Excellence. TVET plays an important role in the educational system; reports from donors and TVET's inclusion in the NPA indicate its value and the further need to develop it.

TVET delivers training services to make Palestinian youth more qualified to enter the Palestinian labour market. Its centers have conducted several training courses to enhance the market competencies of employees in specific skills. TVET began with seven locations, including two industrial schools and five vocational centers at schools in Bethlehem, Jerusalem, Jericho, and Gaza, and has since expanded to 15 centers.

Social Entrepreneurship in Palestine

The emergence of social issues on a global scale has provided an opportunity for young entrepreneurs to engage in social entrepreneurship. Consequently, this change in the overall context has resulted in social start-ups and businesses being recognized as potential solutions to worldwide social problems, forming a part of a global movement (Misbauddin & Nabi, 2019).

However, despite this trend, the development of necessary skills and competencies for social entrepreneurs in Palestine remains inadequate. While there is a growing demand for social entrepreneurship, there is limited understanding regarding the specific abilities that social entrepreneurs need to possess in order to achieve success (Miller et al., 2012). In order to identify and propose the required competencies for social entrepreneurs in Palestine, we are investigating whether any efforts have been made to internationalise the social entrepreneurship process. In the research on social entrepreneurship, little insights have been obtained regarding the internationalisation process, and the competencies needed for this process. However, some studies have investigated the competencies necessary for social entrepreneurs.

In the work by Miller et al. (2012), the authors identify 35 competencies from the literature that social entrepreneurs need in their entrepreneurial efforts, and they further compare these to the educational practices in US higher education. From the study, the authors identify ten competencies that are most important for social entrepreneurs such as the ability to solve problems, interpersonal communication skills, and the ability to develop collaborative relations. The results from this study are further tested by Wronka-Pośpiech (2016) who in her study, identifies ten competencies that she explores in the Polish context. While some of the competencies have the same level of importance, the results show that the social entrepreneurs in the two countries differ to some degree in their views regarding the most important competencies. Hence, in the development of competencies for social entrepreneurs,

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Misbauddin and Nabi (2019) present a conceptual framework for the internationalisation process of social business (SB) based on an in-depth literature review on social entrepreneurship, SB, and the internationalisation of small businesses. Creating a social impact in a foreign location was seen as the main factor behind the internationalisation decision. Other factors were entrepreneur-specific, firm-specific, and context-specific ones. The framework highlights opportunity identification and the internationalisation implementation phases specifically, while their key contribution resides in the visualisation of an internationalisation framework for SB since it points to gaps and directions within this space. The framework's value towards academia is evident but by including information on the antecedents, opportunity exploitation process, and barriers in the way of SB internationalisation, it serves practitioners too, since they can consider it in their expansion efforts and also be made aware of issues required for successful internationalisation. The authors point to the lack of empirical research as a limitation in their work and future research opportunities are the identification of weak points of the framework, its validation and refinement through multiple methodologies, e.g. case studies, etc. change and specify (Misbauddin & Nabi, 2019). The EPISODE project proposes a social innovation competence framework based on the previous work done by Miller et al. (2012) and Misbauddin and Nabi (2019) to focus on actual Palestinian entrepreneurs' needs and educating social entrepreneurs to acquire and improve important competencies towards going international with their social start-ups.

Step Two: Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was precisely carried out, engaging a diverse range of stakeholders, including experts in social entrepreneurship, digital entrepreneurship, and competence development. These experts, comprising academic researchers, practitioners, and educators, brought their unique insights and experiences to the table. Through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, we investigated into understanding the essential competencies crucial for thriving in social digital entrepreneurship. Our examination of EntreComp and DigComp competencies highlighted a suite of competencies. Stakeholders then validated these competencies, with special attention and efforts to align said competencies with the Palestinian context To pinpoint competencies relevant to the Palestinian setting, we developed questions tailored for focus group discussions.

The first face-to-face focus groups were held at An-Najah University and were attended by 30 students from various disciplines who were enrolled in entrepreneurship courses. This session allowed for in-depth discussions and brainstorming among participants with diverse backgrounds and expertise. The physical presence of these students encouraged lively and interactive discussions, enabling the collection of nuanced insights into the specific social competencies required for entrepreneurship in the Palestinian context.

The second focus group was conducted virtually via Zoom and specifically targeted 10 startups. This virtual format facilitated participation from startup founders who are located in different governorates of Palestine. Their experiences and perspectives provided a unique lens on the practical application of social competencies in the real world of entrepreneurship. Please refer to the attached annex for details.

Through these two focus group sessions, the research team gained a comprehensive understanding of the social competencies necessary to successful entrepreneurship in Palestine. The combination of face-to-face and virtual interactions ensured a diverse and representative sample of participants, enriching the data collection process and contributing to the development of a robust competence framework tailored to the Palestinian context.

The main objective of the focus group sessions was identifying the different competencies to be included in the educational tools developed in the EPISODE project. Questions included social entrepreneurship's level of contribution to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, preferred learning approaches, the difference in competencies needed for social entrepreneurship versus traditional entrepreneurship, important competencies for social entrepreneurship, and the respondents' organisation's most important entrepreneurial competencies.

Step Three: Competence Identification and Framework Development

This section focuses on introducing the competencies within the EPISODE social innovation competence framework. It begins with an overview of two competencies, "spotting opportunities" and "mobilizing resources," drawn from the EntreComp framework.

The former involves recognising opportunities for innovation and growth, while the latter focuses on effectively gathering and utilising resources to bring ideas to fruition. Following this, we delve into the importance of identifying social problems and exhibiting cultural awareness, as emphasised by Miller et al. (2012) and Wronka-Pośpiech (2016). Understanding societal challenges and appreciating cultural differences are essential aspects of successful innovation efforts. Additionally, we'll explore digital competencies sourced from the DigComp framework, highlighting the skills needed to leverage digital tools effectively in the realm of social innovation.

Figure 3: EPISODE competence framework.

Spotting Opportunities

In the context of Palestine, social entrepreneurs need to be able to identify opportunities that could contribute to reaching Palestine's goals. These opportunities could be sources of funding, new markets, or collaborations. Hence, having the ability to spot opportunities, entrepreneurs could identify opportunities in the international markets that will enable further expansion for their activity, while at the same time maintaining the sustainable focus existing in the business.

This competence has the following descriptors (Bacigalupo et al., 2016):

- Identify and seize opportunities to create value by exploring the social, cultural and economic landscape.
- Identify needs and challenges that need to be met.
- Establish new connections and bring together scattered elements of the landscape to create opportunities to create value.

The competence therefore has the following themes in which the learning outcomes are organised: Identify, create and seize opportunities; focus on challenges; uncover needs; analyse the context (as shown in Table 1: Spotting Opportunities Themes).

Theme	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Identify, create and seize opportunities	I can find opportunities to help others.	I can recognise opportunities to create value in my community and surroundings	I can explain what makes an opportunity to create value.	I can proactively look for opportunities to create value, including out of necessity.	I can describe different analytical approaches to identify entrepreneurial opportunities.
Focus on challenges.	I can find different examples of challenges that need solutions.	I can recognise challenges in my community and surroundings that I can contribute to solving.	I can identify opportunities to solve problems in alternative ways.	I can redefine the description of a challenge, so that alternative opportunities address it may become apparent.	I can take apart established practices and challenge mainstream thought to create opportunities and look at challenges in different ways.
Uncover needs.	I can find examples of groups who have benefited from a solution to a given problem.	I can identify needs in my community and surroundings that have not been met.	I can explain that different groups may have different needs.	I can establish which user group, and which needs, I want to tackle through creating value.	I can carry out a needs analysis involving relevant stakeholders.

<p>Analyse the context.</p>	<p>I can tell the difference between different areas where value can be created (for example, at home, in the community, in the environment, or in the economy or society).</p>	<p>I can recognise the different roles the public, private and third sectors play in my region or country.</p>	<p>I can tell the difference between contexts for creating value (for example, communities and informal networks, existing organisations, the market).</p>	<p>I can identify my personal, social and professional opportunities for creating value, both in existing organisations or by setting up new ventures.</p>	<p>I can identify the boundaries of the system that are relevant to my (or my team's) value-creating activity.</p>
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Mobilising Resources

To be able to act on the opportunities identified, social entrepreneurs need to be able to mobilise resources to reach their goals. This competence therefore revolves around obtaining and marshalling the necessary resources to be able to conduct the activities as planned. Thus, by being able to mobilise resources, social entrepreneurs could for instance obtain financing for their efforts, onboard necessary individuals, and ensure the optimal and ethical utilisation of obtained resources. This competence has the following descriptors (Bacigalupo et al., 2016):

- Get and manage digital resources needed to turn ideas into actions.
- Make the most of limited resources.
- Get and manage the competences needed at any stage, including technical, legal, tax and digital competences.

As such, the learning objectives for this competence are organised under the following themes: make the most of your time, manage resources (digital); use resources responsibly; get support (as shown in Table 2: Mobilising Resources Themes).

Table 2: Mobilising Resources Themes

Theme	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Make the most of your time.	I can recognise different uses for my time (for example, studying, playing, resting).	I value my time as a scarce resource.	I can discuss the need for investing time in different value-creating activities.	I can use my time effectively to achieve my goals.	I can help others manage their time effectively.
Manage resources (material and non-material).	I recognise that resources are not unlimited.	I can appreciate the importance of sharing resources with others.	I can experiment with different combinations of resources to turn my ideas into action.	I can get and manage the necessary resources to turn my idea into action.	I can get together the necessary resources to develop my value-creating activity.
Use resources responsibly.	I value my possessions and use them responsibly.	I can describe how resources last longer through reuse, repair and recycling.	I can discuss the principles of circular economy and resource efficiency.	I use resources responsibly and efficiently (for example, energy, materials in the supply chain or manufacturing process, public spaces).	I can choose and put in place effective resource-management procedures (for example, life-cycle analysis, solid waste).
Get support.	I can look for help when I am having difficulty achieving what I have decided to do.	I can identify sources of help for my value-creating activity (for example, teachers, peers, mentors).	I can describe the concepts of division of labour and job specialisation.	I can find and list public and private services to support my value-creating activity (for example, incubator, social enterprise advisors, start-up angels, chamber of commerce).	I can find digital solutions (for example, free, paid for, or open-source) that can help me manage my value-creating activities efficiently.

Social understanding and awareness

In the digital era, social understanding and awareness are more crucial and foundational than ever for social entrepreneurs. By harnessing the power of digital tools and platforms, entrepreneurs can create targeted, impactful solutions, engage with communities, innovate ethically, and advocate for positive social change. Additionally, understanding societal dynamics helps in building networks, measuring impact, and staying adaptable and innovative amidst technological advancements. Moreover, ethical considerations are crucial to ensure interventions uphold principles of fairness and inclusivity. Overall, leveraging digital tools with a deep understanding of social contexts empowers social entrepreneurs to drive meaningful change effectively. According to Miller (2012) and Wronak- Pospiech (2016) Cultural Awareness and Identifying Social Problems are essential in this context and this is elaborated in the following sections:

Cultural Awareness

Helping entrepreneurs in understanding the cultural differences that might emerge when moving into different international markets and regions, reducing problems connected to cultural differences. Knowing what is and is not permitted or expected or considered legitimate by social and cultural standards is key to developing successful social entrepreneurial strategies and operational plans (Dacin et al., 2010).

The predominant approach to explore cultural differences is the six cultural dimensions from Hofstede (1980, 2001), which has been extended to nine dimensions in the GLOBE study (House et al., 2004), and further applied in the context of social entrepreneurship (Canestrino et al., 2020). These nine dimensions are Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, In-group Collectivism, Institutional Collectivism, Gender Egalitarianism, Performance Orientation, Future Orientation, Human Orientation and Assertiveness. Based on the above, this competence has the following descriptors:

- Identify and analyse dimensions in another culture.
- See positive and negative aspects of cultures and tolerate differences.
- Manage differences by communicating effectively and see opportunities from having an “outsider perspective”.

The learning objectives for cultural awareness are therefore organised under the following themes: cultural dimensions, tolerance and cultural differences (as shown in Table 3: Cultural Awareness Themes).

Table 3: Cultural Awareness Themes

Theme	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Analyse culture.	I can identify examples of distinct cultural dimensions in other cultures.	I can define specific cultural dimensions that are important for social entrepreneurship	I can describe cultural dimensions that may affect social business opportunities in a given context.	I can manage cultural dimensions which may promote or inhibit social entrepreneurship in a given context.	I can find opportunities for social value-creating activities based on cultural dimensions.
Tolerate differences.	I can identify different practices in solving social needs in my own and in other cultures.	I can non-judgmentally observe practices that may be relevant for social value-creating opportunities.	I can describe positive and negative aspects of how social problems are solved in my own and in other cultures.	I can explain and utilise the reasons why there are different approaches to solve social problems.	I can disagree with other cultural practices without judging and learn from their practices.
Manage differences.	I can identify possible obstacles in communicating with people from another culture.	I can identify specific communication obstacles based on certain cultural dimensions.	I can describe communication techniques that facilitate cooperation despite cultural differences.	I can use my knowledge about a given culture to communicate effectively and facilitate cooperation to solve social needs.	I can identify and reflect upon opportunities and barriers from having an "outsider" perspective when working with my value-creation.

Ability to Identify Social Problems

Social problems exist in many countries, regions and contexts, and as a social entrepreneur, it is necessary to be able to identify social problems in varying situations (Miller et al., 2012).

Different problems require different approaches and solutions, and often the entrepreneur needs to implement innovative solutions, both at the managerial level and in the organisation's solutions (Shaw & Carter, 2007; Zahra et al., 2008). For this to be achieved entrepreneurs need to have insights into the problems, the system of which the problems are embedded in, and the contextual uniqueness and similarity to other contexts. Entrepreneurs need to utilise prior knowledge about the context and be innovative in the understanding of the system to be able to develop sufficient solutions (Zahra et al., 2008).

Moreover, as value creation is central in entrepreneurship, and especially the creation of social value for social entrepreneurs, an understanding of total wealth is needed in the task of identifying social problems (Sullivan Mort et al., 2003; Zahra et al., 2008). Having the necessary insights in the potential of total wealth in a system, that is, the sum of social and economic wealth, will help the entrepreneur understand the problems' complexity in the system in which they exist (Zahra et al., 2008). Thus, the competence ability to identify social problems has the following descriptors:

- Identify and analyse social problems in various contexts.
- Use social wealth as a measure to analyse and discuss social problems.
- Understand the system in which social problems exist, including the efforts needed to initiate processes intended to reduce the social problems.

Furthermore, the learning objectives for the competence are organised under the following themes: systems of social problems; contextual knowledge; social wealth (as shown in Table 4: Ability to Identify Social Problems).

Table 4: Ability to identify Social Problems Themes

Theme	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Understand social wealth.	I can identify different constituents of social wealth: Social value and social costs.	I can identify different levels of social value and social costs.	I can describe the relations and interconnections between social value and costs.	I can evaluate different constituents and combinations of social value and costs in my work to identify those that optimise a solution.	I can evaluate the social values and costs in a system including economic wealth to identify the best solutions.
Utilise contextual knowledge.	I can identify social problems in my context.	I can identify the main driving forces of my context's social problems.	I can identify the characteristics of my context and identify similar contexts with similar social problems.	I can explain and utilise the reasons why there are different approaches to solve social problems.	I can disagree with other cultural practices without judging and learn from their practices.
Analyse the system.	I can identify social problems that exist in a system.	I can identify changes that would reduce the system's social problems.	I can think of well-known approaches that could reduce the system's social problems.	I can imagine new and novel ways of reducing a system's social problems.	I can assess the plausibility whether different solutions fit in the system.

Digital Competencies

Digital competences are of utmost importance for social entrepreneurs seeking to transform their ventures and drive growth. In today's digitally connected world, leveraging digital tools and strategies is essential for maximising the impact and reach of social initiatives. By harnessing digital competences, social entrepreneurs can effectively communicate their mission, engage with diverse stakeholders, and mobilise resources on various digital platforms. They can leverage social media to build a strong online presence, raise awareness about their cause, and foster a community of supporters. Moreover, digital competences enable social entrepreneurs to leverage data analytics and insights to assess the effectiveness of their interventions, identify areas for improvement, and make data-driven decisions. Embracing technology and digital innovations empowers social entrepreneurs to scale their initiatives, optimise their operations, and collaborate with a wider network of partners and beneficiaries. Ultimately, digital competences are instrumental in unlocking the potential of social ventures, facilitating sustainable growth, and creating meaningful social impact in the digital age. Thus, the competence digital integration has the following descriptors:

- Ability to effectively use digital tools, navigate online platforms, and understand basic digital concept
- Collect, analyse, and interpret data using digital tools and techniques.
- Leverage digital channels for marketing and outreach purposes to engage with stakeholders, promote initiatives, and amplify social impact
- Identify and adopt emerging technologies to enhance social innovation and create sustainable solutions

As such, the learning objectives for the competence are organised under the following themes: digital literacy; data analysis; digital marketing, technology innovation and social management(as shown in Table 5: Digital Competence).

Table 5: Digital Competence

Theme	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Digital Literacy	Limited understanding and experience with digital tools, requiring significant assistance for basic tasks	Displays fundamental proficiency in using common digital tools with some guidance	Competently navigates a variety of digital platforms and engages in basic digital collaboration.	Demonstrates strong proficiency in utilizing digital tools, implementing security measures, and contributing to digital communities	Exhibits mastery of digital tools, innovation in problem-solving, and leadership in promoting digital literacy principles

Table 5: Digital Competence

Data Analysis	Limited understanding and proficiency in basic data analysis concepts and techniques, requiring significant guidance	Demonstrates fundamental skills in simple data analysis tasks with some assistance.	Competently analyzes moderately complex data sets and applies statistical methods with minimal guidance	Displays advanced proficiency in analyzing complex data sets, utilizing programming languages, and addressing sophisticated data quality issues	Exhibits mastery in cutting-edge data analysis methods, leading initiatives, and providing mentorship to advance the field
Digital Marketing	Demonstrates basic understanding of digital marketing concepts but lacks practical experience in implementing strategies or campaigns.	Displays proficiency in executing fundamental digital marketing tactics such as social media posting or email marketing with guidance	Exhibits competence in planning and executing digital marketing campaigns across multiple channels, leveraging analytics for optimization	Demonstrates expertise in developing and implementing comprehensive digital marketing strategies, utilizing advanced analytics and targeting techniques.	Displays mastery in leading digital marketing initiatives, innovating strategies and achieving measurable results while also mentoring others in the field
Technology Innovation	Demonstrates basic awareness of technology trends but lacks experience in applying innovative solutions	Displays proficiency in adopting existing technologies for solving routine problems or improving processes	Exhibits competence in identifying and implementing emerging technologies to address specific challenges or opportunities	Demonstrates expertise in leading technology innovation projects, developing novel solutions, and driving organizational change	Displays mastery in shaping industry trends, pioneering disruptive technologies, and fostering a culture of innovation within and beyond the organization
Social Management	Demonstrates basic understanding of social media platforms but lacks experience in managing social media accounts effectively	Displays proficiency in executing routine social media tasks such as posting content and responding to messages under supervision	Exhibits competence in developing and implementing social media strategies, engaging with audiences, and analyzing performance metrics independently	Demonstrates expertise in optimizing social media campaigns, leveraging advanced analytics and audience targeting techniques to drive engagement and conversions	Displays mastery in leading social media initiatives, developing innovative strategies, and fostering strong online communities while mentoring others in social media management

Step Four: Validation Workshop

The fourth step in customising the competence framework for Social entrepreneurship in the Digital Era is the Validation workshop. The main purpose of this step is to ensure the framework's relevance, efficacy, and acceptance within the sector. By bringing together diverse stakeholders including social entrepreneurs, educators, industry experts, a workshop organized to facilitate discussions, feedback gathering, and consensus-building around the key competencies necessary for success in the digital age. This workshop provided a platform for stakeholders to review and validate the proposed framework, ensuring alignment with current needs, challenges, and trends in the field. Moreover, the workshop helped to foster inclusivity by allowing diverse perspectives to be considered, ensuring that the framework reflects the needs of different communities within the social entrepreneurship ecosystem in Palestine. Ultimately, the validation workshop enhanced ownership, buy-in, and adoption of the competence framework, contributing to the advancement and effectiveness of social entrepreneurship in the digital era.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the EPISODE framework aims to boost digital readiness and growth in Palestinian social entrepreneurship. It focuses on several key competence themes:

- Mobilising resources: Building community support, expanding volunteer networks, and mobilising collaborators.
- Spotting opportunities and business development: This theme encourages creativity, foresight, and recognizing new opportunities, while also covering aspects like motivation, resilience, and understanding financial concepts.
- Social understanding and awareness: Prioritising empathy, compassion, identifying social issues, understanding different cultures, and ethical thinking.
- Digital Competencies: Covering digital marketing, basic coding, data analysis, cybersecurity, and online collaboration.

In table below, the different competences in the EPISODE framework are summarised, along with descriptors.

Table 4: Ability to identify Social Problems Themes

Competences	Hints	Descriptors
<p>Spotting opportunities</p>	<p>Use your imagination and abilities to identify opportunities for creating value</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and seize opportunities to create value by exploring the social, cultural and economic landscape • Identify needs and challenges that need to be met • Establish new connections and bring together scattered elements of the landscape to create opportunities to create value
<p>Mobilising resources</p>	<p>Gather and manage the resources you need</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get and manage the material, non-material and digital resources needed to turn ideas into action <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make the most of limited resources • Get and manage the competences needed at any stage, including technical, legal, tax and digital competences
<p>Social Understanding and Awareness</p>	<p>Ability to identify social problems</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and analyse social problems in various contexts • Use social wealth as a measure to analyse and discuss social problems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the system in which social problems exist, including the efforts needed to initiate processes intended to reduce the social problems
	<p>Cultural awareness</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and analyse dimensions in another culture. • See positive and negative aspects of cultures and tolerate differences. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage differences by communicating effectively and see opportunities from having an 'outsider perspective'.

<p style="text-align: center;">Digital Competencies</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Be updated with your digital skills and knowledge</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to effectively use digital tools, navigate online platforms, and understand basic digital concept • Collect, analyse, and interpret data using digital tools and techniques. • Leverage digital channels for marketing and outreach purposes to engage with stakeholders, promote initiatives, and amplify social impact • Identify and adopt emerging technologies to enhance social innovation and create sustainable solutions
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These themes are crucial for empowering aspiring social entrepreneurs in Palestine, addressing challenges, and fostering innovation. The EPISODE framework's successful implementation, focusing on these competencies, can significantly strengthen the social entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Moreover, recognizing the framework's importance, it will lead the development of the next work package in the EPISODE project: designing a training curriculum for social entrepreneurs. By incorporating EPISODE principles into this curriculum, we aim to guide education, training, policy-making, and curriculum development, contributing to economic independence and societal well-being in the region.

10